

ZAMONAVIY O'ZBEK MAHALLALARIDA YOSHLAR BILAN ISHLASHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.

Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir o'g'li

Osiyo xalqaro universiteti, Tarix va filologiya kafedrası o'qituvchisi.

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Annotatsiya. Yangi O'zbekistonda mahallalarga e'tibor davlat siyosati darajasiga ko'tarildi. Mustaqillik yillarida yurtimizda mahalla tizimida misli ko'rilmagan o'zgarishlar amalga oshirildi. Xalqimiz ongi, dunyoqarashi o'zgardi. Rivojlanayotgan yangi O'zbekistonda mahallaning o'rni beqiyos, albatta. Prezident SH. M Mirziyoyev tomonidan mahalla tizimini isloh qilish bo'yicha bir qancha farmon va qarorlar qabul qilindi va amaliyotga joriy qilinmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: mahalla, islohotlar, urf-odat, yoshlar yetakchisi, xokim yordamchisi, ijtimoiy xodim, yoshlar yetakchisi.

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF WORKING WITH YOUTH IN MODERN UZBEK NEIGHBORHOODS.

Abstract. In new Uzbekistan, attention to neighborhoods has risen to the level of state policy. During the years of independence, unprecedented changes have been made in the neighborhood system in our country. The consciousness and worldview of our people have changed. The role of the neighborhood in the developing new Uzbekistan is, of course, incomparable. A number of decrees and resolutions on reforming the neighborhood system have been adopted by President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev and are being implemented.

Keywords: neighborhood, reforms, customs, youth leader, assistant to the governor, social worker, youth leader.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАБОТЫ С МОЛОДЕЖЬЮ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УЗБЕКСКИХ КВАРТАЛАХ.

Аннотация. В новом Узбекистане внимание к микрорайонам возведено в ранг государственной политики. За годы независимости в нашей стране произошли беспрецедентные изменения в системе соседства. Изменилось сознание и мировоззрение нашего народа. Роль махалли в развитии нового Узбекистана, конечно, несравнима. Президент Ш. М. Мирзиёевым принят и реализуется ряд указов и постановлений по реформированию махаллинской системы.

Ключевые слова: район, реформы, традиции, молодежный лидер, помощник губернатора, социальный работник, молодежный лидер.

O'zbekistonda mahallada yoshlar bilan ishlash tizimi so'nggi yillarda sezilarli darajada isloh qilindi va o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega bo'ldi. Bu tizimning asosiy maqsadi – yoshlarning muammolarini bevosita mahallaning o'zida aniqlash, ularni hal etishga ko'maklashish, bo'sh vaqtini mazmunli tashkil etish, kasb-hunarga yo'naltirish va umuman, yoshlar siyosatini eng quyi bo'g'inda samarali amalga oshirishdir. Har bir mahallada Yoshlar yetakchisi lavozimi joriy etilgan. Bu shaxs bevosita mahalladagi yoshlar bilan ishlaydi.

Quyidagilar mahalladagi yoshlar yetakchisining asosiy vazifalaridir.

1. Yoshlar balansini shakllantirish, yoshlar to'g'risidagi zarur ma'lumotlarni “Yoshlar daftari” va “Yoshlar portali” elektron platformalariga kiritib borish, ular bilan samarali ish tashkil qilish

2. Mahallada yoshlarning bo'sh vaqtini mazmunli tashkil etish

3. Yoshlarning ijtimoiy faolligini oshirish, iqtidori, iste'dodi va tashabbuslarni rag'batlantirish hamda hayotda o'z o'rnini topishlariga ko'maklashish

4. Yoshlarni vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalash hamda ularning intellektual jihatdan kamol toptirish

5. Huquqbuzarlik sodir etishga moyilligi bo'lgan yoshlar bilan tizimli ishlash, jazoni ozod etish muassasalaridan ozod qilingan, ixtisoslashtirilgan o'quv –tarbiya muassasalaridan qaytib kelgan yoshlarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik rehabilitatsiya qilinishi va moslashuviga ko'maklashish

Yetakchi Yoshlar ishlari agentligining mahalladagi vakili hisoblanadi va mahalladagi yoshlar siyosatini amalga oshirish uchun mas'uldir. Uning asosiy vazifalari: yoshlar muammolarini o'rganish, "Yoshlar balansi"ni shakllantirish, yoshlarni toifalarga ajratish ("Yoshlar daftari"ga kiritish va u bilan ishlash), tadbirlar tashkil etish, yoshlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash va hokazo. Mahallada ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy masalalarni hal qilishda hamjihatlikni ta'minlash uchun "mahalla yettiligi" (ba'zan "beshlik" yoki "oltilik" bo'lgan, hozirda kengaygan) tizimi ishlaydi. Yoshlar yetakchisi ushbu yettilikning muhim a'zosi hisoblanadi. Bu yettilikka odatda mahalla raisi, hokim yordamchisi, xotin-qizlar faoli, profilaktika inspektori, soliq inspektori, ijtimoiy xodim va yoshlar yetakchisi kiradi. Ular birgalikda mahalladagi muammolarni, shu jumladan yoshlar masalalarini muhokama qiladi va yechim topadi.

Har bir mahallada yashovchi 14 yoshdan 30 yoshgacha bo'lgan barcha yoshlar haqida ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olgan "Yoshlar balansi" shakllantiriladi. Bunda ularning bandligi, ijtimoiy ahvoli, qiziqishlari va muammolari qayd etiladi.

Yoshlar muayyan mezonlar asosida toifalarga ajratiladi (masalan, ishsiz, ijtimoiy himoyaga muhtoj, nogironligi bor, chet eldan qaytgan, huquqbuzarlikka moyil, iqtidorli va hokazo). Ijtimoiy himoyaga muhtoj, ishsiz va muammolari bo'lgan yoshlar "Yoshlar daftari"ga kiritiladi.

Bu daftarga kiritilgan yoshlarga davlat tomonidan manzilli yordam ko'rsatiladi (moddiy yordam, subsidiya, kredit, kasb-hunarga o'qitish, ishga joylashtirish va h.k.). Yoshlar yetakchisi bu jarayonda asosiy rol o'ynaydi.

Tizim har bir yoshning muammosiga individual yondashishga harakat qiladi. "Yoshlar balansi" va kategoriyalash aynan shu maqsadga xizmat qiladi. Tadbirlar va qo'llab-quvvatlash choralari umumiy emas, balki muayyan ehtiyoj va muammolarga qaratilgan bo'ladi.

Yoshlar yetakchilari mahallada sport musobaqalari, madaniy tadbirlar, intellektual o'yinlar ("Zakovat" va b.), kasb-hunarga yo'naltiruvchi uchrashuvlar, kitobxonlik kechalari kabi tadbirlarni muntazam tashkil etib boradi. Yoshlarni turli to'garaklarga (sport, san'at, fan, IT) jalb qilishga harakat qilinadi. Yoshlar yetakchisi o'z faoliyatida tuman (shahar) hokimligi sektorlari, Yoshlar ishlari agentligi bo'limi, Bandlikka ko'maklashish markazi, banklar, ta'lim muassasalari, ichki ishlar organlari va boshqa tashkilotlar bilan yaqin hamkorlikda ishlaydi.

Profilaktika inspektori bilan hamkorlikda huquqbuzarlikka moyil yoki nazoratsiz qolgan yoshlar bilan individual ish olib boriladi. Ularni to'g'ri yo'lga solish, jamoat ishlariga jalb qilish choralari ko'riladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, mahalladagi yoshlar bilan ishlash tizimi – bu Yoshlar yetakchisi markaziy figurali bo'lgan, "Mahalla yetiligi" orqali hamkorlikni ta'minlaydigan, "Yoshlar balansi" va "Yoshlar daftari" kabi vositalar yordamida yoshlarning muammolarini manzilli aniqlab, ularga individual yordam ko'rsatishga qaratilgan kompleks va ko'p qirrali mexanizmdir.

Bu tizim davlatning yoshlar siyosatini bevosita joylarga, har bir yoshga yetkazishga mo'ljallangan

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